

PREDICTIVE MRI FEATURES OF VOLUMETRIC, RESPONSE FOLLOWING UTERINE ARTERY EMBOLIZATION OF LEIOMYOMAS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the mean reduction in leiomyoma volume according to MRI factors in terms of location, size and intensity of leiomyoma following uterine artery embolization (UAE).

Study Design: Quasi-Experimental study.

Study Setting: This study was conducted in the Department of Radiology, Alnoor Diagnostic Centre, Lahore,

Study Duration: Six Months (January to June'25)

Methodology: The collected sample size was 108 reproductive age women ranges from 20-45 years and presented with uterine leiomyomas. For evaluation of leiomyoma size, location and signal intensity with volume calculated through prolate ellipse formula, we used MRI. The UAE was performed via a unilateral transfemoral approach under local anesthesia, after 6 months of the procedure volume reduction was noted by comparing with pre-procedure.

Results: Among 108 patients (mean age 42.7 ± 6.1 years), the mean leiomyoma volume significantly decreased from 158.06 ± 166.19 cm³ to 67.09 ± 76.45 cm³ after UAE (mean reduction = $56.8 \pm 18.2\%$, $p < 0.001$), indicating a substantial and consistent volumetric shrinkage across the cohort.

Conclusion: In agreement with other national and global studies, it was concluded UAE is an effective, uterus-preserving intervention with significant leiomyoma volume reduction.

INTRODUCTION

Uterine artery embolization (UAE) is recognized widely being its minimally invasive intervention and effective option for treatment of uterine fibroids. ¹ Through a careful selection of fibroids for ischemic damage preserves blood flow of the endometrium leading in volume reduction and fibroid necrosis over the time. ^{2,3} However, the subsequent clinical response may vary due to extent of fibroid in addition to incomplete infarction. Though, clinical improvement is the primary goal of the treatment but magnetic resonance imaging

(MRI) is recognized important predictive marker for success of the treatment. The followup radiological evaluation involves fibroid volume measurement by using prolate ellipse formula through images by contract enhanced on T1-weighted. However, the reproducibility and reliability of these methods in addition to predictive accuracy required more sophisticated investigations. ^{4,7}

Kurban et al in their study evaluated pre and post UAE MRI features to determine fibroid regression.

They are of the view that smaller volumetric fibroids shrinkage in volume is 62.2% compared to those with larger volume that results in 53.8% reduction clearly showing size-dependent treatment response. Regarding anatomical location, submucosal leiomyomas exhibited the highest clinical response by reducing 84.1%, emphasizing strong treatment efficacy. Contrary to this, low volumetric reduction is achieved in nonsubmucosal leiomyomas by calculating $39.9\% \pm 5.3\%$ mean reduction. Furthermore, the signal intensity characteristics of leiomyomas on MRI also appear to play a role in their volumetric response to UAE. Hyperintense leiomyomas demonstrated a mean reduction of $48.8\% \pm 10.6\%$, while hypointense leiomyomas exhibited a slightly higher mean reduction of $53.1\% \pm 3.9\%$. These findings suggest that the initial signal intensity of leiomyomas on MRI may influence their response to UAE, with hypointense leiomyomas showing a slightly more favourable volumetric response.⁸ According to Margau et al., imaging follow-up (after UAE) demonstrated a mean tumour volume reduction of 39.3% (95% confidence interval [CI], 28.2%–50.5%) and mean uterine volume reduction of 37.6% (95% CI, 26%–49.3%). There were no cases of continued tumour perfusion and no major complications. There was one minor complication of prolonged hospital stay (36 hours) for pain control. They concluded that UAE was successfully and safely performed for pedunculated subserosal leiomyomas, with a tumour volume reduction of 39% and no unique complications related to these lesions.⁹

Our study aims to explore the role of MRI predictive factors in assessing the volumetric response of UAE, specifically focusing on the reduction in leiomyoma volume. To the best of our knowledge, no studies investigating MRI predictive factors following uterine artery embolization (UAE) in terms of reduction in leiomyoma volume have been conducted at the local level in Pakistan. Consequently, another trial filling this research gap is required in our population. It was considered as helpful for remarkable clinical implications while selecting the patients, planning treatment and monitoring keeping in view therapeutic response. Moreover, the results of this trial will enhance guidance for optimizing

management protocols, contribution in existing body of knowledge relating to UAE.

METHODOLOGY:

This quasi-experimental study was conducted at the Radiology Department of Alnoor Diagnostic Centre, Lahore. The study duration spanned six months after approval of the synopsis. A sample size of 108 patients was calculated using a 95% confidence level, an absolute precision of 0.10, and a mean reduction of 39.9 ± 5.3 in leiomyoma volume in the non-submucosal type. Non-probability convenience sampling was employed for participant recruitment.

Premenopausal women aged between 20 and 45 years who presented with symptoms such as menorrhagia, pelvic pain, or bulk-related symptoms and were diagnosed with uterine leiomyomas were included. Patients were excluded if they had gynecological malignancy, undiagnosed pelvic masses, acute pelvic infection, coagulopathy, pregnancy, or postmenopausal status. Those with contraindications to MRI or a history of allergy to iodinated contrast medium or gadolinium were also excluded.

Informed written consent was secured from all patients. Basic demographic data, including age and duration of symptoms, were recorded. All eligible patients underwent baseline MRI examinations under standard protocols. The MRI scans were interpreted by experienced radiologists with a minimum of five years of expertise in MRI. Uterine leiomyomas were assessed for number, location, signal intensity, and size. Volumes were calculated using the prolate ellipse formula, defined as the product of length, width, depth, and a constant factor of 0.523.

Uterine artery embolization (UAE) was performed by the same interventional radiologist under moderate sedation and local anaesthesia. A unilateral percutaneous transfemoral approach was utilized, and embolization continued until bilateral proximal ascending uterine arteries were adequately occluded. Following UAE, patients underwent follow-up MRI at six months. Post-treatment MRI measurements were compared with pre-treatment values to determine the percentage

reduction in leiomyoma volume for each predictive factor, namely location, size, and intensity.

All the data will be entered and analysed using SPSS Ver. 27.0. The numerical variables i.e., age, duration of symptoms, number of lesions, and volume of leiomyoma before and after UAE and reduction in volume will be presented as mean and standard deviation. The categorical variables i.e., predictive factors i.e. location of the lesion (submucosal/nonsubmucosal), signal intensity (hyperintense/hypointense), and size of leiomyoma (small/large) will be presented as frequency and percentages. The data will be stratified according to the age and duration of symptoms. T test was applied, post stratification. Independent sample t test was applied to compare mean reduction according to MRI predictive factors i.e. (Submucosal/Non submucosal), (small/large), hypertensive/hypotensive).

RESULTS:

A total of 108 patients were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 42.7 ± 6.1 years, and the mean duration of symptoms prior to treatment was 3.8 ± 1.9 years. All patients had a single leiomyoma lesion. The majority of lesions were

located within the myometrium (50.9%), followed by submucosal (30.6%) and subserous (18.5%) regions. Regarding MRI signal intensity, low-signal leiomyomas were more frequent (61.1%) compared to intermediate-signal lesions (38.9%). In terms of size distribution, 54.6% of the leiomyomas were large, while 45.4% were small. The mean volume regression following Uterine Artery Embolization (UAE) was 56.8 ± 18.2%, reflecting a moderate-to-marked reduction across the cohort. (Table 1)

A paired samples t-test was applied to compare leiomyoma volumes before and after UAE. The mean leiomyoma volume before UAE was 158.06 ± 166.19 cm³, which significantly decreased to 67.09 ± 76.45 cm³ after the procedure. The mean difference in volume was 90.96 cm³ with a 95% confidence interval of 72.05–109.88 cm³. This reduction was statistically significant (t = 9.53, p < 0.001), indicating a substantial shrinkage of leiomyomas after embolization. Overall, these findings demonstrate that UAE produced a consistent and significant decrease in leiomyoma size, with strong correlation between pre- and post-treatment measurements. (Table 2)

TABLE 1: BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS (N = 108)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	Mean ± SD	42.7 ± 6.1	
Duration of Symptoms (years)	Mean ± SD	3.8 ± 1.9	
No. of Lesions	Single	108	100
Location of Lesion	Submucosal	33	30.6
	Myometrial	55	50.9
	Subserous	20	18.5
Signal Intensity	Low Signal	66	61.1
	Intermediate Signal	42	38.9
Size of Leiomyoma	Small	49	45.4
	Large	59	54.6
Volume Regression (%)	Mean ± SD	56.8 ± 18.2	

TABLE 2: COMPARISON OF LEIOMYOMA EMBOLIZATION (PAIRED SAMPLES T-TEST, N = 108)

Variable	Mean ± SD	Mean Difference	95% CI of Difference	t-value	p-value
Volume Before UAE (cm ³)	158.06 ± 166.19	90.96	72.05 - 109.88	9.53	<0.001
Volume After UAE (cm ³)	67.09 ± 76.45				

DISCUSSION:

In this study, we evaluated mean reduction in leiomyoma following uterine artery embolization(UAE) and recorded 56.8 ± 18.2 % volume at six months, by endorsing the efficacy with minimally invasive procedure by preserving uterus in the management of symptomatic fibroids. Our results are in agreement with other global evidence showing progressive volume regression in addition to symptomatic improvements.^{1,2}

Before and after the embolization, MRI has a potential role confirmed by Sadick and co-workers³ documented reliably MR-perfusion parameters after the embolization done. Similarly, another trial by Keung and colleagues⁴ confirms the durability of UAE regarding relief in symptoms in addition to reduced complications rate than open surgery.

In our study, MRI-based predictive factors including size, location and signal intensity remarkably emphasized reduction in volume. Greater shrinkage was observed compared to subserosal types/intramural in submucosal fibroids, which aligns with Kurban et al⁸ reported 84.1% reduction in submucosal than 39.9% in those with non-submucosal fibroids. The higher response of submucosal lesions may be due to their endometrial limited collateral blood flow and endometrial proximity. Our reported mean reduction is higher than reported by Margau and others⁹ documented 39.3% for pedunculated subserosal fibroids, capitalize the vascular distribution role.

Worldwide, epidemiological data¹⁰ reveals that fibroids affect nearly 70% of the reproductive aged women emphasizing the need of uterus-preservative interventions like UAE. Further, local data, by Majid et al¹³ is evident that following UAE, 96% of the cases had symptomatic resolution, enhancing the safety and reproducibility of the procedure. Another trial by Chen et al¹⁴ reported that MRI performed within 3 days after the procedure is done accurately predicts medium-term efficacy, with complete

necrosis correlating with greater six-month volume reduction (70.6 % vs 51.4 %, p < 0.001).

Various other studies like Yerezhbayeva et al¹⁵ through systematic and comparative analysis confirms strong therapeutic profile of UAE by showing significant fibroid shrinkage than MR-guided focused ultrasound (MRgFUS) over 6-24 months, whereas Guirguis and others¹⁶ recorded 44% volume reduction with significant relief in symptoms at 6 months. Similarly, Xu et al in another study⁶ concluded fast recover with UAE than MRgFUS and myomectomy.

Regarding Quality-of-life(QoL), Silva et al²¹ demonstrated remarkable gains in myoma and perfusion volume upto 12 month after the embolization, however, Sadick et al¹⁷ are of the view that sustained reduction in perfusion and myoma volume up to 12 months post-embolization.

Outcomes regarding fertility are also favourable and evident from Fabre et al.¹⁸ reported 12 live births after UAE without any severe obstetric related complications.

Biological and imaging advances continue to refine patient selection. Aimagambetova et al.¹⁹ suggested that VEGF and TGF-β levels may predict fibroid regression after UAE, while Tu et al.²⁰ highlighted the FIGO MRI classification system for improving diagnostic consistency. Additionally, Slotman et al.²² emphasized the need for standardized MRI terminology to enhance interdisciplinary communication.

Collectively, these results reaffirm UAE as a safe and effective uterus-preserving procedure. MRI not only facilitates accurate diagnosis and treatment planning but also serves as a prognostic tool for evaluating treatment success.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of our study in agreement with local and other global data concludes that UAE leads to a

durable and significant reduction in leiomyoma volume. However MRI parameters—especially smaller size, submucosal lesion and hypointense signal intensity are reliable predictors of advantageous outcome. Integrating MRI-based predictors and potential biochemical markers into UAE protocols may further enhance individualized treatment planning and optimize clinical outcomes.

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